

Extending Petri Nets with Transition Weights to Improve Model-Checking using Monte Carlo Simulations

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Abstract. We introduce transition weights in Petri nets to perform Monte Carlo simulations, to avoid the state-space explosion problem, for verification of reachability cardinality properties. The presented algorithms are implemented in the TAPAAL engine. We present an online algorithm for transition selection, and prove its correctness, which shows an increase in performance when used. Monte Carlo simulations are implemented using the online algorithm, and we adapt interesting transitions to decrease computational overhead. We find that implementing a set of interesting transitions that only had to be computed once is most beneficial. We then implement three heuristics to guide the Monte Carlo simulations, and compare it against TAPAAL search strategies, for verification of reachability cardinality properties. The results show that our search strategy finds answers, which are not found by TAPAAL.

1 Introduction

Model-checking techniques for labeled transition systems are used to answer property formulas with an absolute guarantee of correctness [3]. These techniques are in practice hard to work with, or even impossible due to the state-space explosion problem. An alternative is statistical model-checking [13] (SMC) of probabilistic systems. Systems are subject to various stochastic properties such as message loss or garbling. Such properties can be modeled and verified, by using transition systems where transitions are chosen based on probabilities instead of nondeterministically.

Even with a less rigid notion of guarantee, probabilistic systems can still become too time-consuming and costly for experiments. Monte Carlo simulation [8] is an SMC method, combining a model with a randomization factor to simulate the behavior of the model. Instead of exhaustive computations of probabilities, properties are observed for a given amount of simulations, where the probability of reaching a property is estimated using the number of times the property is observed.

Using SMC techniques, such as Monte Carlo simulations, is accepted in a wide range of research areas such as systems biology or chemical processes. Depending on the model to be analyzed, different state-of-the-art tools can be used

to verify properties of the model. Among these tools are UPPAAL STRATEGO [7], combining various branches of UPPAAL [4], offering SMC support for stochastic priced timed games using sequential hypothesis testing, or Monte Carlo simulation. VESTA [16] and MRMC [10] are model checkers for Markovian models, both able to verify probabilistic computation tree logic [3] (PCTL) and continuous stochastic logic [2] (CSL) properties.

ORIS [15] and GREATSPN [1] are model checking tools for stochastic Petri nets. ORIS uses earliest and latest firing times, and a cumulative distribution function to analyze the behavior of models. GREATSPN also uses firing rates, and weights can be added to transitions to specify the probability of choosing immediate transitions.

Adding weights to all transitions has shown promising results [12] as an extension to Petri nets. In this paper we present an extension to Petri nets, allowing probabilistic behavior with transition weights. We implement it in the TAPAAL [6] engine, a model checker for timed-arc Petri nets. We use transition weights to implement Monte Carlo simulations, and study techniques to reduce computational overhead, to determine if this is a valid search strategy for reachability cardinality properties. We propose an online algorithm for transition selection based on transition weights, to eliminate the use of unnecessary memory. Using the online algorithm, we implement Monte Carlo simulations, and adapt the use of *interesting transitions* to make the verification more efficient. Lastly, we develop different heuristics to guide the search of reachability properties. We compare the Monte Carlo algorithm with search heuristics against TAPAAL search strategies on models and properties from the Model Checking Contest 2021 [11] (MCC2021).

In Section 2, we present preliminary theory of Petri nets with inhibitor arcs, and extend the model to include a probabilistic weight property. We then present the syntax for reachability properties. In Section 3, we introduce a naive and an online algorithm to select transitions for Monte Carlo simulations in Petri nets, and perform an experiment to determine the possible benefits of the online algorithm. In Section 4, we introduce an algorithm for statistical model checking of reachability properties in Petri nets using Monte Carlo simulation, and enhance the algorithm with the use of interesting transitions. In Section 5, we introduce different heuristics to use the proposed Monte Carlo algorithm as a search strategy for reachability cardinality properties and compare it against search strategies implemented in TAPAAL.

The code implemented for the project can be found on the GitHub repository <https://github.com/fulei345/verifypn>. Instructions for reconstructing the project experiments and data can be found on the main branch in the `readme.md` file in the `reproduce.zip` file.

2 Preliminaries

In Section 2.1 we present Petri nets with inhibitor arcs. In Section 2.2 we extend the Petri net definition with a weight property on transitions. In Section 2.3 we present the syntax of reachability properties.

2.1 Petri Nets with Inhibitor Arcs

A Petri net is a directed bi-partite graph [14]. The nodes in a Petri net can be divided into places and transitions, graphically represented with circles and boxes. An example of this is shown in Figure 1, with a Petri net that models a communication protocol. Transitions can be seen as events in the modeled system. Places can be seen as conditions, where input places to a transition describe the pre-conditions of an event, and output places describe the post-condition of the event. Edges, or arcs, can go from a place to a transition, or from a transition to a place. Arcs are labeled with a positive integer weight. The label for arcs with a weight of 1 are omitted in the graphical representation. Petri nets can be extended with a set of inhibitor arcs. Inhibitor arcs go from a place to a transition, and are graphically represented with a circle instead of an arrowhead. Inhibitor arcs are also labeled with a positive integer weight. A transition with an ingoing inhibitor arc can only fire if the place that the inhibitor arc originates from is marked with less tokens than the specified label. A marking, i.e. the state of the net, assigns a nonnegative integer to all places. A place marked with an integer k is said to be marked with k tokens. Tokens are shown as dots inside places. A formal definition of Petri nets with inhibitor arcs is given in Definition 1.

Definition 1 (Petri nets with Inhibitor Arcs [14]). *A Petri net with inhibitor arcs is a 6-tuple $N = (P, T, F, W, I, W_I)$ where,*

- P is a finite set of places,
- T is a finite set of transitions, where $P \cap T = \emptyset$,
- $F \subseteq (P \times T) \cup (T \times P)$ is a set of arcs,
- $W : F \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a weight function on arcs,
- $I \subseteq P \times T$ is a set of inhibitor arcs,
- $W_I : I \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a weight function on inhibitor arcs.

A marking M on a Petri net N is a function $M : P \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^0$. An initial marking is denoted as M_0 . A Petri net with an initial marking is a pair (N, M_0) . The set of all markings for a Petri net N is denoted as $\mathcal{M}(N)$.

Example 1. The Petri net N shown in Figure 1 models a communication protocol. The place p_1 models a sender ready to send a message, and p_2 models a receiver ready to receive a message. A message can be sent by firing the transition t_1 , which adds a token to the places p_3 and p_5 . The message can be received from the buffer p_5 by firing t_2 , adding a token to the place p_4 . The receiver can

Fig. 1: An example of a Petri net modeling a communication protocol

then send an acknowledgement modeled by transition t_4 , adding a token to the acknowledgement buffer p_6 , and p_2 . The sender can resend the message with the transition t_6 , if no token has been added to p_6 . Resending the message adds two tokens to p_5 . The transition t_3 allows the sender to receive the acknowledgement, and become ready to send a new message. The Petri net also models the event of a message being dropped with the transition t_5 .

The behavior and change of states in Petri nets with inhibitor arcs is non-deterministic. A change of state happens when a transition is *fired*. For a transition to fire it must be an *enabled* transition. The set $enabled(N, M)$ contains all enabled transitions in the Petri net N given the marking M , as defined in Definition 2.

Definition 2 (Enabled Transitions). For all $t \in T$, $t \in enabled(N, M)$ iff for all $p \in P$ it holds that $M(p) \geq W((p, t))$ if $(p, t) \in F$ and $M(p) < W_I((p, t))$ if $(p, t) \in I$.

From the set of enabled transitions, a transition is nondeterministically chosen to be fired. When a transition $t \in enabled(N, M)$ is fired in marking M the marking is changed to marking M' , denoted $M \xrightarrow{t} M'$. $W((p, t))$ tokens are removed from each input place p of t , if $(p, t) \in F$, and $W((t, p'))$ tokens are added to p' at each output place p' of t , as defined in Definition 3.

Definition 3 (Firing Transition). A transition $t \in enabled(N, M)$ can fire in marking M , producing marking M' , written as $M \xrightarrow{t} M'$, where $M'(p) = M(p) - W((p, t)) + W((t, p'))$ for every $p \in P$.

2.2 Probabilistic Petri Nets with Inhibitor Arcs

To facilitate statistical model checking in Petri nets, we extend Petri nets with a weight on transitions. A *potency* is added to all transitions, s.t. transitions are no longer chosen nondeterministically, but instead based on probability. Probabilistic Petri nets are defined in Definition 4.

Definition 4 (Probabilistic Petri Nets with Inhibitor Arcs). *Probabilistic Petri nets with inhibitor arcs extend Petri nets with inhibitor arcs $N = (P, T, F, W, I, W_I)$ with a potency function Y :*

$$- Y : T \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$$

The function $Y(t)$, where $t \in T$, returns the potency of the transition.

A potency k on transition t is graphically represented by adding the potency in front of the transition name, i.e. $k : t$. A potency of 1 can be omitted from the graphical representation. An example of potencies added to transitions is shown in Figure 1. The probability of firing an enabled transition t in marking M is defined in Definition 5. The probability is found by dividing the potency of t with the total potency of all enabled transitions.

Definition 5 (Firing Transition Probability). *The probability of firing an enabled transition t in marking M is given by the function $prob(t, M)$:*

$$prob(t, M) = \frac{Y(t)}{\sum_{t \in enabled(N, M)} Y(t)} \quad (1)$$

The function $prob(t, M)$ ensures a proper distribution over enabled transitions, as defined in Lemma 1.

Lemma 1. *The function $prob(t, M)$ ensures a proper distribution, s.t.*

$$\sum_{t \in enabled(N, M)} prob(t, M) = 1 \quad (2)$$

In the case of a deadlock no transitions are enabled, and as such no probability distribution exists for firing transitions.

2.3 Reachability Property Syntax

To define a property ϕ for a probabilistic Petri net $N = (P, T, F, W, I, W_I, Y)$ we present the *reachability logic* from the Model Checking Contest [11]:

$$\phi ::= true \mid false \mid \alpha \mid deadlock \mid \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \mid \phi_1 \vee \phi_2 \mid \neg \phi$$

$$\alpha ::= t \mid e_1 \bowtie e_2$$

$$e ::= c \mid p \mid e_1 \oplus e_2$$

where $p \in P$, $t \in T$, $c \in \mathbb{N}^0$, $\bowtie \in \{<, \leq, =, \neq, \geq, >\}$, and $\oplus \in \{+, -, \cdot\}$. Arithmetic expressions can be evaluated in a marking M , and the evaluations are defined as $eval_M(c) = c$, $eval_M(p) = M(p)$, and $eval_M(e_1 \oplus e_2) = eval_M(e_1) \oplus eval_M(e_2)$. The semantics of whether a reachability formula ϕ holds in a marking

M is defined as:

$$M \models \text{true}$$

$$M \not\models \text{false}$$

$$M \models t \text{ iff } t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$$

$$M \models \text{deadlock} \text{ iff } \text{enabled}(N, M) = \emptyset$$

$$M \models e_1 \bowtie e_2 \text{ iff } \text{eval}_M(e_1) \bowtie \text{eval}_M(e_2)$$

$$M \models \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \text{ iff } M \models \phi_1 \text{ and } M \models \phi_2$$

$$M \models \phi_1 \vee \phi_2 \text{ iff } M \models \phi_1 \text{ or } M \models \phi_2$$

$$M \models \neg\phi \text{ iff } M \not\models \phi$$

Example 2. Consider the Petri net N in Figure 1. An example of a property that can be satisfied is $\phi ::= p_5 \geq 10$. An example of a property that can not be satisfied is $\phi ::= p_2 = 10$.

3 Non-Uniform Transition Choice Algorithm

To implement Monte Carlo simulations a randomization factor is needed to simulate the behavior of a given Petri net. This can be implemented with the use of potencies for transition weights and a random number generator. To ensure that the correct behavior is simulated, all transitions $t \in T$ must be selected with a probability of $\text{prob}(t, M)$ for a marking M .

In Section 3.1 we present a naive algorithm to select transitions. In Section 3.2 we propose an online algorithm to select transitions, and prove that the algorithm selects transitions with the correct probability. In Section 3.3 we present an experiment comparing the time it takes to select and fire transitions for the presented algorithms.

3.1 Naive Transition Choice Algorithm

A naive algorithm for selecting transitions is presented in Algorithm 1. A variable n is first used to store the total potency across all enabled transitions. To select a transition, a random number between 0 and n is then selected. If marking M is a deadlock state, none of the loops are entered and \perp is returned. As the first loop sums the potencies of all enabled transitions, it is trivial to verify, that the algorithm selects a transition t with probability equal to Equation (1).

Algorithm 1 iterates the set of enabled transitions twice in the worst case, and depending on the implementation of the set of enabled transitions, an array

Algorithm 1 A naive algorithm for selecting a transition $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$ with probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$

Input: Petri net N , marking M
Output: Transition t , where $t \in \text{enabled}(t, M)$ and t is selected with probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$, or \perp if M is a deadlock state

```

1:  $n \leftarrow 0$ 
2: for  $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$  do
3:    $n \leftarrow n + Y(t)$ 
4: end for
5:  $r \leftarrow$  a random integer in  $[0, n]$ 
6:  $n \leftarrow 0$ 
7: for  $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$  do
8:    $n \leftarrow n + Y(t)$ 
9:   if  $r \leq n$  then
10:    return  $t$ 
11:   end if
12: end for
13: return  $\perp$ 
    
```

might be needed to store the iterated transitions. Iterating the set of enabled transitions twice, and storing transitions when it is not needed can cause problems for large Petri net models. As Monte Carlo simulations require transitions to be chosen often, we implement an algorithm that can select transitions with a single iteration of the set of enabled transitions and without using unnecessary memory.

3.2 Online Transition Choice Algorithm

An online algorithm for selecting an enabled transition to fire, based on potency, is presented in Algorithm 2. The for-loop on Line 3 iterates the set of enabled transitions $\text{enabled}(N, M) = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$. The variable n is used to keep track of the sum of all preceding transition potencies. In the i th iteration of the for-loop $current$ is assigned to t_i with the probability of its potency divided by n . The algorithm returns the last transition assigned to $current$, or \perp if the marking M is a deadlock state.

We prove that Algorithm 2 selects an enabled transition t in marking M with the probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$. The theorem is presented in Theorem 1. The proof for Theorem 1 uses Lemma 2. We assume the set $\text{enabled}(N, M) = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ is enumerated from 1 to n and t_i is the transition processed in the i th iteration of the for-loop.

Lemma 2. *In Algorithm 2, the variable $current$ is assigned to transition $t_i \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$ on Line 7 in the i th iteration of the for-loop with the probability:*

$$\frac{Y(t_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)} \quad (3)$$

Algorithm 2 An online algorithm for selecting a transition $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$ with probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$

Input: Petri net N , marking M
Output: Transition t , where $t \in \text{enabled}(t, M)$ and t is selected with probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$, or \perp if M is in a deadlock

```

1:  $current \leftarrow \perp$ 
2:  $n \leftarrow 0$ 
3: for  $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$  do
4:    $n \leftarrow n + Y(t)$ 
5:    $r \leftarrow$  a random number in  $[0, 1]$ 
6:   if  $r \leq Y(t)/n$  then
7:      $current \leftarrow t$ 
8:   end if
9: end for
10: return  $current$ 

```

Proof. Lemma 2 is proven by an induction on i .

Inductive hypothesis on i , $IH(i)$:

At iteration i it holds that variable $n = \sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)$, after Line 4 is executed.

Base case - $IH(1)$:

On Line 2, n is initialized to 0. On Line 4, $Y(t_1)$ is added to n , meaning $n = Y(t_1)$.

Inductive case - $IH(i)$:

Assume for the i th iteration that $n = \sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)$, after Line 4 is executed. Then, for $i + 1$, n is updated to $(\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)) + Y(t_{i+1})$ on Line 4, which is equal to $\sum_{j=1}^{i+1} Y(t_j)$.

Conclusion:

Given the base case and the inductive case, it is implied that the inductive hypothesis holds for all i . Given that the inductive hypothesis holds it can be concluded that Lemma 2 is correct. As n is proven to be equal to $\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)$ on Line 6, and r is a random number, Line 7 is executed with a probability equal to Equation (3). ■

Theorem 1 (Transition Choice Correctness). *Algorithm 2 selects transition t in marking M with the probability $\text{prob}(t, M)$.*

Proof. Assume a Petri net N and a marking M where the set $\text{enabled}(N, M) = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$. A transition $t_i \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$ is chosen in the i th iteration of the for-loop with the probability equal to Equation (3). The probability of keeping the transition in the $i + 1$ th iteration of the for-loop is then equal to Equation (4).

$$\frac{Y(t_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{Y(t_{i+1})}{\sum_{j=1}^{i+1} Y(t_j)} \right) \quad (4)$$

The probability of keeping transition t_i from the i th to the n th iteration can be generalized to Equation (5).

$$\frac{Y(t_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)} \prod_{k=i+1}^n \left(1 - \frac{Y(t_k)}{\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j)} \right) \quad (5)$$

Subtracting the fraction from 1 can be rewritten to Equation (6).

$$\frac{Y(t_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^i Y(t_j)} \prod_{k=i+1}^n \frac{\left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right) - Y(t_k)}{\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j)} \quad (6)$$

The multiplication of fractions can be written into one fraction resulting in Equation (7).

$$\frac{Y(t_i) \prod_{k=i+1}^n \left(\left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right) - Y(t_k) \right)}{\prod_{k=i}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right)} \quad (7)$$

Subtracting $Y(t_k)$ from the summation can be reduced to Equation (8).

$$\frac{Y(t_i) \prod_{k=i+1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} Y(t_j) \right)}{\prod_{k=i}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right)} \quad (8)$$

Which is equal to Equation (9).

$$\frac{Y(t_i) \prod_{k=i}^{n-1} \left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right)}{\prod_{k=i}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^k Y(t_j) \right)} \quad (9)$$

The multiplications in the numerator and denominator can be reduced to Equation (10).

$$\frac{Y(t_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n Y(t_j)} \quad (10)$$

Which is equal to the definition of the function $prob(t, M)$. ■

Example 3. Consider the Petri net N in Figure 1, and the marking M where $M(p_3) = 1$, $M(p_5) = 1$, and $M(p) = 0$ for all other $p \in P$. In the marking M the set of enabled transitions is $enabled(N, M) = \{t_2, t_5, t_6\}$, and the potency of the enabled transitions are $Y(t_2) = 90$, $Y(t_5) = 9$, and $Y(t_6) = 1$. The probabilities of selecting the transitions are:

$$\begin{aligned} prob(t_2, M) &= 90/100 = 0.9 \\ prob(t_5, M) &= 9/100 = 0.09 \\ prob(t_6, M) &= 1/100 = 0.01 \end{aligned}$$

A visual representation of using Algorithm 2 to choose an enabled transition in marking M is shown in Figure 2. At each node in the tree a probabilistic choice is made between keeping the current transition or selecting a new transition.

Fig. 2: Tree representation of using Algorithm 2 to choose a transition

The probability of choosing a transition is equal to the product of probabilities, from the root to each leaf marked by the given transition, summed up. In Equation (11) the edges to transition t_6 are summed up, to find the probability of choosing the transition.

$$(90/90) \cdot (90/99) \cdot (1/100) + (90/90) \cdot (9/99) \cdot (1/100) = 0.01 \quad (11)$$

3.3 Algorithm Comparison Experiment

We conduct an experiment to determine the benefit of using the online Algorithm 2, compared to the naive Algorithm 1. The experiments are conducted such that each algorithm fires 1.000.000 transitions. The algorithms are only compared by the time spent on selecting transitions and firing them. The hypothesis is that Algorithm 2 is faster, as it is not slowed down by storing all enabled transitions in an array. The models used in the experiments are from the Model Checking Contest 2021 [11] (MCC2021). The MCC2021 provides 1.181 models, on which each algorithm is run. A non-uniform distribution is simulated by generating random potencies between 1 and 100 for each transition on all models. If one of the algorithms does not fire all transitions, i.e. the model has a deadlock, the model is not considered. The experiments are run five times, with a 15 minute timeout, and the median of the five recorded times is used as the result. This is done to eliminate the variance between runs.

For 342 models, both algorithms are able to fire all transitions before time out. In Figure 3, the time it takes each algorithm to fire the transitions is sorted independently. In general, it can be observed that Algorithm 1 spends more time selecting and firing transitions.

Naive vs. Online Median Times

Fig. 3: Sorted time in seconds taken to select and fire 1.000.000 transitions across 342 models for the naive Algorithm 1 and online Algorithm 2

In Figure 4, the time spent by the online algorithm is divided by the time spent by the naive algorithm, to obtain the ratio. 10 out of 342 models have a ratio above 1, and the average ratio is 0.87. The results show that the hypothesis of Algorithm 2 executing the fastest is correct, and a benefit is gained by using the algorithm. Algorithm 2 is used moving forward.

4 Property Verification using Monte Carlo Simulations

With the Petri net model and randomization factor to select transitions, Monte Carlo simulations can be performed on Petri nets using a looping control structure. This can be further extended to verify reachability properties in the Petri net, by evaluating the given property every time a new marking is reached. The amount of *runs* to simulate in the Petri net can be specified, and a counter can then be used to count the runs that reach a marking which satisfy the property. A *depth* can be specified to determine the amount of transitions to fire before the control loop should terminate.

In Section 4.1 we present an algorithm to verify reachability properties, by simulating runs in a Petri net, which returns the probability of reaching the property in a run. We adapt the use of *interesting transitions* [5] to reduce computational overhead. In Section 4.2 we define a set of interesting transitions, which only needs to be computed once. In Section 4.3 we present an experiment to determine which set of presented interesting transitions is most beneficial for the Monte Carlo algorithm.

Fig. 4: Time taken by the online algorithm divided by the time taken by the naive algorithm, sorted to determine the ratio of time spent

4.1 Monte Carlo Simulation Algorithm

Algorithm 3 can be used to compute the probability of a run in a Petri net N satisfying some reachability property ϕ . The algorithm input specifies the amount of runs to simulate, and how many transitions to fire within a run. An outer-loop controls the run count, and an inner-loop controls the depth of the run. When a new run is started the marking is reset on Line 5. Assuming a left to right evaluation of conditions, if a transition has been chosen, it is checked if the transition is in the set of interesting transitions on Line 8. The property ϕ is evaluated in the current marking M on Line 9. A transition is selected with Algorithm 2 on Line 14.

Remark 1. For an execution of Algorithm 3 where the probabilistic choices are the same, e.g. using a seed to generate random numbers, increasing the *run* and *depth* variables does not decrease the amount of runs evaluating a property ϕ as satisfied in some marking M .

In Algorithm 3, a property ϕ is evaluated if the last transition fired is in the set of interesting transitions $interest(\phi, N, M)$. A possible set of interesting transitions is all transitions $t \in T$ in a Petri net N . We will denote $interest(\phi, N, M) = T$ as $A_T(\phi)$. Using $A_T(\phi)$ may be inefficient as most transitions $t \in T$ may *never* change marking M , where $M \not\models \phi$, to a marking M' , where $M' \models \phi$.

To make Algorithm 3 more efficient, we first adapt the set of interesting transitions $A_M(\phi) \subseteq T$, presented in [5]. $A_M(\phi)$ is defined for a marking M

Algorithm 3 Compute probability of satisfying a reachability property ϕ in a run of Petri net N

Input: Petri net N , property to verify ϕ , number of runs $runs$, number of transitions to fire in each run $depth$

Output: Probability of reaching property ϕ in Petri net N

```

1:  $current\_runs \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $property\_count \leftarrow 0$ 
3: while  $current\_runs < runs$  do
4:    $current\_depth \leftarrow 0$ 
5:    $M \leftarrow initialMarking(N)$ 
6:    $t \leftarrow \perp$ 
7:   do
8:     if ( $t = \perp$  or  $t \in interest(\phi, N, M)$ ) then
9:       if  $M \models \phi$  then
10:         $property\_count \leftarrow property\_count + 1$ 
11:        break
12:      end if
13:    end if
14:     $t \leftarrow selectTransition(N, M)$   $\triangleright$  returns  $\perp$  if  $M$  is in a deadlock
15:    if  $t \neq \perp$  then
16:       $M \leftarrow fire(t, N, M)$ 
17:       $current\_depth \leftarrow current\_depth + 1$ 
18:    end if
19:    while  $current\_depth < depth$  and  $t \neq \perp$ 
20:       $current\_runs \leftarrow current\_runs + 1$ 
21:    end while
22: return  $property\_count/runs$ 

```

relative to a property ϕ . Intuitively, a transition $t \in A_M(\phi)$ is a transition that may change the marking M of a Petri net N , to a marking M' , where $M' \models \phi$. Whenever a sequence of transitions $w = t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n \in T^*$ is fired, $M \xrightarrow{w} M'$, where $M \not\models \phi$ and $M' \models \phi$, there must exist an i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, s.t. $t_i \in A_M(\phi)$. This is an important property of interesting transitions. $A_M(\phi)$ is further defined in [5].

4.2 A Less Strict Interesting Transitions Set

The set of transitions $A_M(\phi)$ is specific for a marking M , and has to be recomputed every time a transition $t \in A_M(\phi)$ is fired. We now define a set of transitions $A_0(\phi) \subseteq T$ as a less strict version of $A_M(\phi)$, s.t. the relation $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi) \subseteq A_T(\phi)$ holds. The intuition is that $A_0(\phi)$ is precomputed once in the initial marking M_0 , and does not need to be updated.

To define $A_0(\phi)$ we adapt the following notation from [5]. For a place or transition x , let the *preset* of x be denoted as $\bullet x = \{y \mid W((y, x)) > 0\}$, and the *postset* of x as $x^\bullet = \{y \mid W((x, y)) > 0\}$. For a place p let the *increasing preset* of p , containing all transitions that increase the number of tokens in p ,

ϕ	$A_0(\phi)$	$A_M(\phi)$
<i>deadlock</i>	T	$(\bullet t)^- \cup {}^+(\circ t)$ for some $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$
t	${}^+(\bullet t) \cup (\circ t)^-$	${}^+p$ for some $p \in \bullet t$ where $M(p) < W(p, t)$ or p^- for some $p \in \circ t$ where $M(p) \geq I(p, t)$
$e_1 = e_2$	$\text{incr}_M(e_1) \cup \text{decr}_M(e_1) \cup$ $\text{incr}_M(e_2) \cup \text{decr}_M(e_2)$	$\text{decr}_M(e_1) \cup \text{incr}_M(e_2)$ if $\text{eval}_M(e_2) > \text{eval}_M(e_1)$ $\text{incr}_M(e_1) \cup \text{decr}_M(e_2)$ if $\text{eval}_M(e_2) < \text{eval}_M(e_1)$
$\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2$	$A_0(\phi_1) \cup A_0(\phi_2)$	$A_M(\phi_i)$ for some $i \in \{1, 2\}$ where $M \not\models \phi_i$

Table 1: $A_0(\phi)$ and $A_M(\phi)$ [5] for the cases where they are different

be defined as ${}^+p = \{t \in \bullet p \mid W((t, p)) > W((p, t))\}$, and the *decreasing postset* of p as $p^- = \{t \in p^\bullet \mid W((t, p)) < W((p, t))\}$. For a transition t , let the *inhibitor preset* of t be defined as $\circ t = \{p \mid I((p, t)) < \infty\}$, and for a place p , let the *inhibitor postset* of p be defined as $p^\circ = \{t \mid I((p, t)) < \infty\}$.

The definition of $A_0(\phi)$ is given in Table 2. The functions $\text{incr}_M : E_N \rightarrow 2^T$ and $\text{decr}_M : E_N \rightarrow 2^T$, where E_N is the set of all arithmetic expressions that can be constructed for a Petri net N , are presented in Table 3. Given an expression e the functions return all transitions that can increase or decrease the evaluation of e [5]. The functions have the property presented in Lemma 3.

With the definition of $A_0(\phi)$ we can show that $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi) \subseteq A_T(\phi)$ holds. The relation $A_0(\phi) \subseteq A_T(\phi)$ is trivial to show, as the definition of $A_0(\phi)$ clearly results in a set smaller than or equal to $A_T(\phi)$. The relation $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ can be verified by observing the differences in definitions of $A_M(\phi)$ and $A_0(\phi)$. The differences are shown in Table 1, and argued for below:

- $\phi ::= \text{deadlock}$: $A_M(\phi)$ contains $(\bullet t)^- \cup {}^+(\circ t)$ for some $t \in \text{enabled}(N, M)$. $A_0(\phi)$ is equal to T , so clearly $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$.
- $\phi ::= t$: $A_M(\phi)$ contains ${}^+p$ for some $p \in \bullet t$ where $M(p) < W((p, t))$ or p^- for some $p \in \circ t$ where $M(p) \geq I((p, t))$. $A_0(\phi)$ contains both sets of transitions, i.e. ${}^+(\bullet t) \cup (\circ t)^-$, meaning that $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$.
- $\phi ::= e_1 = e_2$: $A_M(\phi)$ contains either $\text{decr}_M(e_1)$ or $\text{incr}_M(e_1)$, and the opposite set for e_2 , depending on the evaluation of $e_1 = e_2$. $A_0(\phi)$ contains both increment and decrement sets for e_1 and e_2 , meaning that $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$.
- $\phi ::= \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2$: $A_M(\phi)$ contains either $A_M(\phi_1)$ or $A_M(\phi_2)$. $A_0(\phi)$ contains both $A_0(\phi_1)$ and $A_0(\phi_2)$, meaning that $A_M(\phi) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$.

We now present and prove Theorem 2 using Lemma 3, which is presented and proven in [5]. Let $\overline{A_0(\phi)}$ denote the set $T \setminus A_0(\phi)$ of non-interesting transitions.

ϕ	$A_0(\phi)$	$A_0(\neg\phi)$
<i>deadlock</i>	T	\emptyset
t	$+(\bullet t) \cup ({}^\circ t)^-$	$(\bullet t)^- \cup +({}^\circ t)$
$e_1 < e_2$	$decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 \geq e_2)$
$e_1 \leq e_2$	$decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 > e_2)$
$e_1 > e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 \leq e_2)$
$e_1 \geq e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 < e_2)$
$e_1 = e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 \neq e_2)$
$e_1 \neq e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$A_0(e_1 = e_2)$
$\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2$	$A_0(\phi_1) \cup A_0(\phi_2)$	$A_0(\neg\phi_1 \vee \neg\phi_2)$
$\phi_1 \vee \phi_2$	$A_0(\phi_1) \cup A_0(\phi_2)$	$A_0(\neg\phi_1 \wedge \neg\phi_2)$

Table 2: Interesting transitions of a property ϕ for all markings $M \in \mathcal{M}(N)$, where $M \not\models \phi$, otherwise $A_0(\phi) = \emptyset$

Expression e	$incr_M(e)$	$decr_M(e)$
c	\emptyset	\emptyset
p	$+p$	p^-
$e_1 + e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2)$	$decr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_2)$
$e_1 - e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2)$
$e_1 \cdot e_2$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_1) \cup$ $incr_M(e_2) \cup decr_M(e_2)$	$incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_1) \cup$ $incr_M(e_2) \cup decr_M(e_2)$

Table 3: Functions $incr_M$ and $decr_M$ returning all transitions that increase or decrease the amount of tokens in places of an expression

Lemma 3 ([5]). *Let e be an arithmetic expression, let $M, M' \in \mathcal{M}(N)$, and let $w = t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n \in T^*$ be a sequence of transitions, s.t. $M \xrightarrow{w} M'$.*

- If $eval_M(e) < eval_{M'}(e)$ then there is an $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, s.t. $t_i \in incr_M(e)$.
- If $eval_M(e) > eval_{M'}(e)$ then there is an $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, s.t. $t_i \in decr_M(e)$.

Theorem 2. *Let $N = (P, T, F, W, I, W_I)$ be a Petri net, $M \in \mathcal{M}(N)$ a marking, ϕ a reachability property, and $w \in A_0(\phi)^*$ a sequence of non-interesting transitions. If $M \not\models \phi$ and $M \xrightarrow{w} M'$ then $M' \not\models \phi$.*

Proof. Let $N = (P, T, F, W, I, W_I)$ be a Petri net, $M \in \mathcal{M}(N)$ be a marking, and ϕ a given formula. Assume that $M \not\models \phi$. The proof proceeds by structural induction on ϕ .

$\phi ::= \text{deadlock}$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $M' \not\models \phi$ since $A_0(\phi) = T$ resulting in an empty sequence of transitions $w = \epsilon$. As the sequence of transitions w is empty, it is implied that $M = M'$.

$\phi ::= \neg \text{deadlock}$: If $M \not\models \phi$ the model is in a deadlock meaning that $M' \not\models \phi$ as $enabled(N, M) = \emptyset$. As the marking M is a deadlock state, and

$enabled(N, M) = \emptyset$, it is implied that $M = M'$.

$\phi ::= t$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $t \notin enabled(N, M)$. Either there exists $p \in \bullet t$, s.t. $M(p) < W(p, t)$, and we have to fire some transition from ${}^+p$ to enable t , or there exists $p \in {}^\circ t$, s.t. $M(p) \geq I(p, t)$, and we have to fire some transition from p^- to enable t . Since ${}^+p \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ or $p^- \subseteq A_0(\phi)$, we get that $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= \neg t$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $t \in enabled(N, M)$. To disable t we have to fire at least one transition from $(\bullet t)^- \cup {}^+(\circ t)$ to either remove or add tokens that will disable or inhibit t respectively. Since $(\bullet t)^- \cup {}^+(\circ t) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ we have that $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= e_1 < e_2$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $eval_M(e_1) \geq eval_M(e_2)$. Since $decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ we know that $eval_M(e_1) \geq eval_{M'}(e_1)$ as well as $eval_M(e_2) \leq eval_{M'}(e_2)$ because of Lemma 3, and therefore $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= e_1 > e_2$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $eval_M(e_1) \leq eval_M(e_2)$. Since $incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_2) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ we know that $eval_M(e_1) \leq eval_{M'}(e_1)$ as well as $eval_M(e_2) \geq eval_{M'}(e_2)$ because of Lemma 3, and therefore $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= e_1 = e_2$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $eval_M(e_1) \neq eval_M(e_2)$. Since $incr_M(e_1) \cup decr_M(e_1) \cup incr_M(e_2) \cup decr_M(e_2) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ we know that $eval_M(e_1) = eval_{M'}(e_1)$ as well as $eval_M(e_2) = eval_{M'}(e_2)$ because of Lemma 3, and therefore $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then there exists $i \in \{1, 2\}$ s.t. $M \not\models \phi_i$. We know that $A(\phi_i) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ which by the induction hypothesis implies $M' \not\models \phi_i$. By the semantics of conjunction we also have that $M' \not\models \phi$.

$\phi ::= \phi_1 \vee \phi_2$: If $M \not\models \phi$ then $M \not\models \phi_1$ and $M \not\models \phi_2$. We know that $A(\phi_1) \cup A(\phi_2) \subseteq A_0(\phi)$ which by the induction hypothesis implies $M' \not\models \phi_1$ and $M' \not\models \phi_2$. By semantics of disjunction we also have that $M' \not\models \phi$.

The remaining cases and negation cases are analogous. ■

Example 4. Consider the Petri net N in Figure 1 and the reachability property $\phi ::= p_1 \geq 1 \wedge p_1 = p_6$. The frequency at which the property is evaluated, in Algorithm 3 on Line 9, depends on whether $A_T(\phi)$, $A_0(\phi)$, or $A_M(\phi)$ is used as the set of interesting transitions. If $A_T(\phi)$ is used the property is evaluated when any transition $t \in T$ is fired.

If the set $A_0(\phi)$ is used, the set of interesting transitions $\{t_1, t_3, t_4\}$ is pre-computed before a run. The set never changes when Algorithm 3 is executing a run, and the property ϕ is evaluated when one of the transitions in the set is fired.

If the set $A_M(\phi)$ is used, the set of interesting transitions is computed for the initial marking, and updated when a transition in the set is fired. For the initial marking the set is $\{t_1, t_4\}$, as 1 token is already placed in p_1 . When transition t_1

Computation Time per Fired Transition

Fig. 5: Time spent computing each set of interesting transitions per transition fired on a logarithmic scale

is fired the set is computed again and updated to $\{t_3\}$, as p_1 has 0 tokens. The set is then updated when transition t_3 is fired.

Assuming that the sequence of transition t_1, t_2, t_4 , and t_3 is fired repeatedly, we can observe that for $A_T(\phi)$ the property ϕ is evaluated every time a transition is fired, for $A_0(\phi)$ ϕ is evaluated every time t_1, t_4 , and t_3 are fired, and for $A_M(\phi)$ ϕ is evaluated every time t_1 , and t_3 is fired.

4.3 Interesting Transition Experiment

Algorithm 3 can be changed, s.t. instead of returning a probability of reaching a property ϕ , it returns *true* if a marking satisfying ϕ is reached on Line 10. Line 22 can be changed to return *unknown*, indicating that the property ϕ could not be verified within the given run count and depth. The algorithm is not able to determine if a property is false. We conduct an experiment on the performance of Algorithm 3 with these changes and run it with the sets $A_M(\phi)$, $A_0(\phi)$ and $A_T(\phi)$. The experiment is conducted to determine which set is most beneficial for evaluating the given property ϕ less.

The experiments are conducted with models and reachability properties from the MCC2021 [11]. 1.181 models are provided by the MCC2021, each with a set of 16 reachability properties, resulting in a total of 18.896 properties to verify. Cardinality reachability properties are specified s.t. the property must either eventually hold for some marking, or it must hold for all markings. Algorithm 3 can only be used to verify properties where the existence can be proven by a witness-trace, which is essentially what a run encapsulates. Algorithm 3 can not

Fig. 6: Number of evaluations of the property ϕ for the run where a marking M is reached, s.t. $M \models \phi$. The results are presented on a logarithmic scale

verify that a property holds in all markings, as this requires an exhaustive state-space search, but it can be used to verify that the negation of the property is reached, disproving the non-negated property.

We run the experiments with a run count of 10.000 and a depth of 10.000. The experiment is conducted with a five minute timeout, and each combination of model and property is run five times to eliminate the variance between runs. The random number generation to select transitions is seeded, s.t. the same transitions are fired for a given run, meaning that the only varying factor is the interesting transition set. This is done to make sure that the implementation of the interesting transition set is the only difference. All results are timed in microseconds, and are presented on a logarithmic scale.

In Figure 5 the amount of time spent computing each interesting transition set is divided by the amount of transitions fired before the property ϕ is verified, resulting in the amount of computation time per fired transition. No time is spent computing the set $A_T(\phi)$. The time for the set $A_M(\phi)$ is accumulated for all updates of the set. The $A_0(\phi)$ is only computed once in the initial marking. Most of the average computation times are under 10 microseconds.

In Figure 6 the amount of times the property ϕ is evaluated is plotted in nondecreasing order. The amount of evaluations is only counted for the run reaching a marking M , where $M \models \phi$. The relation between the graphs is as expected; $A_T(\phi)$ evaluates the property ϕ at every transition fired, and $A_0(\phi)$ evaluates a few more times than the more strict $A_M(\phi)$.

In Figure 7 the computation time of each set of interesting transitions, and the time spent evaluating the property ϕ is summed. The transition firing time

Computation and Evaluation Time

Fig. 7: Total time for computation of interesting transitions and evaluation of property ϕ on a logarithmic scale

has been omitted from this, as it made up over 90% time spent when executing Algorithm 3, which would dictate the graph curve. Trivial properties can be evaluated using $A_T(\phi)$ without much overhead, but the crossing point for $A_T(\phi)$ and $A_0(\phi)$ is at 50 microseconds, meaning that very little time is lost if the set $A_0(\phi)$ is used all the time. We conclude that $A_0(\phi)$ should be used for Monte Carlo simulations in Petri nets. This set of interesting transitions will be used moving forward for all remaining experiments.

5 Heuristic Guided Search

The implementation of Algorithm 3, where *true* or *unknown* is returned, can be further extended with different heuristics. In Section 5.1 we introduce three different heuristics, and give an example showing how they adjust potencies. In Section 5.2 we compare Algorithm 3 with heuristics against search strategies implemented in TAPAAL.

5.1 Heuristics for Guided Monte Carlo Simulations

We introduce three heuristics to guide the runs in Algorithm 3 towards a given reachability property ϕ . The heuristics can be used individually or in combination. All heuristics change the potencies of transitions, and the changes are saved across the runs of Algorithm 3, s.t. the following run can benefit from what is learned in the previous runs.

A measure of distance between a marking and a reachability property is introduced in [9], and is used in TAPAAL for the BestFS heuristic. The distance is the difference in tokens for all places p in a marking M in a given reachability cardinality property. The distance will be used for two of the three heuristics to update transition potencies.

- **Static Heuristic:** The potencies for all transitions in the set of interesting transitions are increased before the first run.
- **Distance Heuristic:** When a transition t is fired in a marking M , $M \xrightarrow{t} M'$, the new marking M' is compared against the previous marking based on their respective distance to the reachability property. If the new marking M' is closer in distance to the property, compared to M , the potency of t is increased, and if it is further away, the potency of t is decreased.
- **Closest Heuristic:** The fired transitions for a run in Algorithm 3 and the shortest distance to the reachability property seen in the run is stored. When the final transition has been fired, the potencies of all fired transitions in the run up to the point where the shortest distance is seen are incremented and the next transition fired after that point is decremented. If the shortest distance is seen multiple times, the first time it is seen is used, since this provides the shortest path to this distance. If the shortest distance is seen in the initial marking, the potencies is instead decremented for all fired transitions in the run.

To ensure that the heuristics do not introduce too much bias for runs in Algorithm 3, the potencies of all transitions can be multiplied by some factor before the first run. As an example, if all potencies are initially multiplied by ten, and the distance heuristic is used, an increment of one does not affect the transition probability choice excessively.

Example 5. Consider the Petri net N in Figure 1, the reachability property $\phi ::= p_5 \geq 10$, and using the interesting transition set $A_0(\phi)$. We now consider how the three different heuristics can update transition potencies in a run of Algorithm 3 with a depth of five. We assume that the transitions t_1 , t_2 , t_4 , t_3 , and t_1 are fired in order. The distance from the initial marking M_0 to the property ϕ is 10, since 10 tokens are missing in the place p_5 .

- **Static Heuristic:** The potencies of the two transitions in $A_0(\phi)$, t_1 and t_6 , are multiplied by 10 before the run.
- **Distance Heuristic:** The transition t_1 is fired, decreasing the distance from 10 to 9, as the reached marking M now has a token in p_5 , and the potency for t_1 is increased. Transition t_2 increases the distance to 10, as a token is removed from p_5 , and the potency of t_2 is therefore decreased. The transitions t_4 and t_3 do not change the amount of tokens in p_5 keeping the distance unchanged, and the potencies of the transitions are therefore not changed. Finally, transition t_1 is fired again, decreasing the distance to 9 and the potency for t_1 is increased.

- **Closest Heuristic:** The five transitions are fired and the distances are observed. The lowest distance observed is 9, which is seen two times. The first time is after the first firing of t_1 , meaning the path to this marking only includes t_1 . The potency of t_1 is therefore increased, and the potency of t_2 is decreased.

5.2 Search Strategy Experiment

We conduct an experiment to determine how Algorithm 3 performs with different search heuristics, compared against search strategies implemented in TAPAAL. The algorithm will be compared against the best-first-search (BestFS) heuristic, breadth-first-search (BFS), and depth-first-search (DFS). All the search strategies will be used to verify reachability properties in Petri net models from the MCC2021. A total of 1.181 models exists, with 16 reachability cardinality properties, resulting in a total of 18.896 properties to verify. A five minute timeout is set for each property.

In Algorithm 3 we use $A_0(\phi)$ and a run count of 1.000.000, but it will run until the five minute timeout, and set the depth to 10.000. The potency for all transitions is initially set to 10 for all experiments. The parameters for the heuristics used in Algorithm 3 are as follows:

- **Static:** The potencies of interesting transitions are set to 100.
- **Distance:** Transition potencies are incremented/decremented by 1.
- **Closest:** Transition potencies are incremented/decremented by 1.

Before the search strategies are applied, 8.323 out of the 18.896 properties are solved by linear programming or property simplifications. 142 properties are solved by applying net reductions. The search strategies are applied to the remaining 10.431 properties. In Figure 8 all times taken to verify these properties are presented and sorted by time spent. We observe that the TAPAAL search strategies are faster for most properties, but Algorithm 3 with heuristics verify more properties before the timeout. A possible reason for more answers is that the Monte Carlo algorithm is not limited by the use of memory, and longer runs do not require more memory. This implies that the TAPAAL search strategies are optimal to use for general property verification, but Algorithm 3 with heuristics can be used to find exclusive answers.

The three heuristics are individually compared to the search strategies implemented in TAPAAL. The results of each of them are presented in Tables 4 to 6. Experiments are also conducted using combinations of the three heuristics for Algorithm 3. The best combination is the use of the static and distance heuristic. The results are presented Table 7. The first result column is the number of properties verified by the given search strategy. The number of timeouts column counts the amount of times a strategy could not verify a property within the five minute limit. The winner column is the number of times a strategy is the fastest to verify the given property, where all strategies solved the property. The solo answer column is the number of times a strategy is the only strategy verifying the property within the time limit.

Search Strategy Verification Times

Fig. 8: Time taken in microseconds by TAPAAL search strategies, each Algorithm 3 heuristic, and the combination of the Static and Distance heuristic.

We observe that Algorithm 3 with heuristics can be used to find exclusive answers. Three of the four heuristics are able to find more answers in total, compared to TAPAAL search strategies. The Static heuristic is able to find the most solo answers, among the three heuristics, and the Distance heuristic is able to find the most answers. Combining the two heuristics showed the best results, as both the amount of answers and solo answers increased. Worth noting is the best performing single heuristic for Algorithm 3, the Static heuristic, is based on the use of interesting transitions.

Search Strategies	Answers	Timeouts	Winner	Solo Answer
BFS	6988	3444	967	18
DFS	8182	2250	1752	32
BestFS	8345	2087	1561	117
Static Heuristic	8482	2088	1832	782

Table 4: Results for Algorithm 3 with the Static heuristic compared to the TAPAAL search strategies.

Search Strategies	Answers	Timeouts	Winner	Solo Answer
BFS	6988	3444	993	29
DFS	8182	2250	1889	30
BestFS	8345	2087	1703	90
Distance Heuristic	8641	1937	1598	773

Table 5: Results for Algorithm 3 with the Distance heuristic compared to the TAPAAL search strategies.

Search Strategies	Answers	Timeouts	Winner	Solo Answer
BFS	6988	3444	1009	25
DFS	8182	2250	1960	31
BestFS	8345	2087	1895	134
Closest Heuristic	8208	2366	1151	710

Table 6: Results for Algorithm 3 with the Closest Heuristic compared to the TAPAAL search strategies.

Search Strategies	Answers	Timeouts	Winner	Solo Answer
BFS	6988	3444	976	20
DFS	8182	2250	1774	30
BestFS	8345	2087	1592	86
Static + Distance	8778	1795	1891	825

Table 7: Results for Algorithm 3 with the Static + Distance heuristic compared to the TAPAAL search strategies.

6 Conclusion

We developed an online algorithm to select transitions without unnecessary memory use, which showed a noticeable improvement, compared to a naive algorithm, storing every enabled transition. We then developed a Monte Carlo algorithm for verification of reachability properties in Petri nets, using the proposed online algorithm. To make the Monte Carlo algorithm more efficient, we adapted the use of interesting transitions. We found that precomputing a set of interesting transitions showed noticeable improvements in property verification. Lastly, we developed three heuristics to guide the Monte Carlo algorithm, such that reachability properties could be verified in fewer runs. Using the heuristic guided Monte Carlo algorithm we were able to find exclusive answers not found by the TAPAAL search strategies. Though the Monte Carlo algorithm found exclusive answers, the results showed that the TAPAAL search strategies found properties faster in most cases.

We conclude that Monte Carlo simulations guided by heuristics for Petri nets show promise as an addition to current verification methods. Current TAPAAL verification methods (BestFS, DFS, BFS) verify properties the fastest most of the time, but the implemented Monte Carlo algorithm finds exclusive answers, for properties where current methods time out, making it a solid extension to the TAPAAL toolbox.

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